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JIS

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

Vision

“ENRICHING BEAUTIFUL MINDS TOWARDS INTELLIGENT MINDS”

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) aims to disseminate scholarly research articles and papers to the wider community with the aim of offering an academic and scientific platform that provides an outlet to authors. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an open access online journal. Initially, the JIS will provide an online version, but is planning a print version later in this academic journey. The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) focuses on a high-quality academic research articles and papers. All categories of research are of interest to the JIS, including insightful empirical studies, conceptual papers, commentary, essays, and theoretical articles.

JIS is an interdisciplinary platform and invites authors, academics, students, researchers, leaders, managers, scientists for their contributions in the disciplines of sciences, sociology, education, philosophy, humanities and management. Articles and Papers of scientific and academic rigour in Qualitative, Quantitative, Mixed or Blend methods are welcome.

JIS intends to publish two issues per annum (May and November).

Submissions to, and Publication in, the JIS is free.

All papers submitted for publication will be peer reviewed.

Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS)

mission is to “Guide Beautiful Minds towards Intellectual Enrichment”

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Editorial

Dear Readers,

The journey of publishing and publication is never a final destination. Once a publication is released, we have another destination to prepare for. The motivation towards consistent publication is a drive derived from the author(s), who wishes to disseminate their valuable knowledge through the Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) platform.

JIS has always been interested to enhance its capacity by assimilating the publication from multi-disciplinary areas. It is our belief that the readers from multi-disciplinary areas can reach the articles of their interest published under one open access platform.

In this current publication, Volume 6, Issue, 1, papers are published within the areas of philosophy, psychology, music and literature.

Our next issue will be published in November 2022 for which we invite researchers, managers, leaders, scientists, students and others for paper submission. The call for paper submission is also announced in the journal's announcement portal <http://journalofinterdisciplinarysciences.com/announcement/>

The Journal of Interdisciplinary Sciences (JIS) is an online open access journal, which offers free submissions, free publication and open access to download its published research paper from the journal's website <http://journalofinterdisciplinarysciences.com/>

It is recommended that all author(s) submitting their manuscript to JIS are advised to read the author guidelines from the journal website

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Let us join and collaborate together to **ENRICH the BEAUTIFUL MINDS
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Mani Man Singh Rajbhandari. Ph.D.
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